

Pupils' Number Knowledge Readiness

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Abstract

Preparing students for school involves equipping them with the necessary skills to learn and excel, such as through play, communication, focus, and social interaction. Ensuring children have a solid foundation in basic number skills before delving into more advanced mathematical concepts is crucial for their academic development. This study focused on evaluating the readiness of Grade 1 students at St. Paul University Surigao in terms of their number knowledge. This involved 24 Grade 1 students and utilized a pretest-post-test design, using a School Readiness Test (SRT) to assess their number knowledge readiness. Data analysis included frequency count and percentage distributions, and paired t-test. The results indicated a significant improvement in the students' number knowledge readiness following the teaching and learning activities, suggesting that these interventions were effective. Furthermore, the study found that factors such as sex and previous school attended did not influence the students' readiness in number knowledge. It is recommended that the school continues implementing activities that enhance students' performance in this area.

Keywords: *number knowledge, readiness, learners, pretest-post-test design, Philippines.*

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Introduction

School readiness encompasses a child's preparedness for a smooth transition into the school environment, with a focus on ensuring they possess the necessary skills for optimal learning readiness. It refers to whether a child is ready to make an easy and successful transition into school (Kid Sense, 2023).

This proactive approach involves engaging children in activities that foster skills essential for their successful integration into the school setting. Key aspects of school

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readiness include a child's ability to concentrate on tasks, exhibit interest in learning, and demonstrate curiosity. At St. Paul University Surigao, the Guidance and Counseling Office utilizes the School Readiness Test (SRT) to evaluate a child's readiness for first grade, aiding educators in assessing and supporting students effectively.

The SRT comprises seven subtests, covering areas such as vocabulary, letter identification, visual discrimination, phonemic awareness, comprehension, number knowledge, and developmental spelling. This study specifically focuses on number knowledge to identify and address any gaps in mathematical understanding, enabling tailored activities to enhance students' proficiency in this subject.

Each item in the number knowledge component requires the student to mark the numeral or figure called for by specific directions. The test samples number meaning, numeral recognition, recognizing order among numbers, recognizing fractional parts, recognizing common measures of time and money, and informal understandings of applied basic processes.

Recent PISA test results revealed that only a small percentage of Filipino students achieved at least a basic level of proficiency in mathematics, prompting a closer examination of learners' number knowledge readiness and its potential impact on mathematical proficiency. Specifically, only 16% of Filipino students attained at least the basic or baseline level of proficiency in mathematics (labeled in the report as “level 2 proficiency”) (Chi, 2023).

Given the lack of formal research on this topic, the researchers embarked on this study to evaluate the number knowledge readiness of Grade 1 students at St. Paul University Surigao. The outcomes of this research will inform future curriculum enhancements aimed at better preparing students to achieve higher levels of mathematical proficiency.

Materials and Methods

This study employed quantitative quasi-experimental research using a pretest-post-test design where the dependent variable is measured once before the treatment is implemented and once after it is implemented (Chiang et al., 2015). This study was conducted to the Grade 1 students at St. Paul University Surigao during the School Year 2023-2024.

The main instrument used in this study is the School Readiness Test (SRT) from the Guidance and Counselling Office wherein it was given as pre-test and post-test to assess the number knowledge readiness of the pupils. This test is an assessment tool that is used to help assist the school and educational professionals in determining a child's readiness for first grade.

To analyze the gathered data, frequency count and percentage distribution and paired t-test were used. Frequency count and percentage distribution were utilized to describe the demographic profile of participants, specifically focusing on sex and previous school. The same tool was used to describe the number knowledge readiness of the learners in both the pre- and post-tests. Paired t-test was used to test significant differences between the pre- and post-test results, focusing on the number knowledge of the learners.

Results

Profile of the Respondents

Table 1. Distribution of Participants According to Demographic Profile

Profile	f (n=24)	%
Sex		
Male	12	50.00
Female	12	50.00
Previous School		
School 1	1	4.17
School 2	1	4.17
School 3	1	4.17
School 4	8	33.33
School 5	1	4.17
School 6	11	45.83
School 7	1	4.17

Table 1 reveals that the respondents in this study were evenly distributed as to their sex with 12 (50.00%) males and 12 (50.00%) females.

The respondents' *previous school* included a wide range of institutions. School 6 had the most respondents, 11 out of 24 (45.83%), followed by School 4 with 8 (33.33%). Schools 1, 2, 3, 5, and 7 had one (4.17%) respondent each. The distribution of respondents across these schools suggests a diverse group of participants, which can be useful for gathering a wide range of experiences and perspectives.

Table 2. Pre- and Post-Test Performance of the Grade 1 Pupils

Performance	Pre-Test		Post-Test	
	f	n	f	n
Definitely Needs Help	4	16.67	2	8.33
Probably Needs Help	10	41.67	4	16.67
OK	10	41.67	18	75.00

As reflected in Table 2, the Pre-test finding shows that 10 (41.67%) of the grade 1 pupils were classified as OK and Probably Needs Help, respectively. Moreover, 4 (16.67%) of the pupils were classified as Definitely Needs Help. This implies that the development of the skills is such that little or no interference with early learning can be anticipated. It also indicates that the pupils show a degree of inadequacy in the skill development that will probably interfere with early learning, as they were also classified as probably needs help. The pupils could use help in development.

For the Post-test finding, it shows that 18 (75.00%) were classified as OK which means that the development of the skills is such that little or no interference with early learning can be anticipated. In addition, 4 (16.67%) were classified as Probably Needs Help which indicates that the pupils show a degree of inadequacy in the skill development that will probably interfere with early learning. The pupils could use help in development. Lastly, 2 (8.33%) of the pupils were classified as Definitely Needs Help which means that the pupils show inadequacies in the development of this underlying skill, sufficient to interfere with early learning.

Table 3. Significant Differences on the Pre- and Post-test Results

Tests	Paired Differences		t	df	p-value	Interpretation
	Mean	SD				
Pre-Test vs Post-Test	-2.46	3.35	-3.60	23	0.002	Significant

Table 3 reveals that there is a significant difference in the Pre- and Post-test results considering that the computed p-value of approximately .002 is lower than the expected level of significance, 0.05, which leads to the rejection of the hypothesis. This implies that there is sufficient evidence that there is a significant increase ($t=-3.60$) in the Pre-test result with Post-test result. This means that the pupils performed better in the post test as indicated in the mean difference which is -2.46.

The difference in the performance can be attributed to the conducted teaching-learning activities by the teacher. Since the pre-test was given during the beginning of the school year, it implies that the learners used their prior knowledge to answer the questions being asked. Then, within the year, they were exposed to activities in mathematics that helped them understand better the concepts which is evidenced in the increase of their performance in the posttest. This is true because in a related study conducted by Arpilleda et al. (2023), the intervention improved learner performance and addressed least-mastered competencies. Although the present study did not talk about intervention and least-mastered competencies, but it is still related since the learners were given discussion and activities that helped them become number knowledge ready.

Table 4. Significant Differences on the Pre- and Post-test Results when Grouped According to the Profile Variables

Profile	Test	F	p-values	Interpretation
Sex	Pre-test	0.03	0.861	Not Significant
	Post-Test	0.00	1.000	Not Significant
Previous School	Pre-test	1.83	0.154	Not Significant
	Post-Test	2.05	0.115	Not Significant

Table 4 presents the significant differences on the pre- and post-test results when grouped according to the profile variables in terms of *sex* and *previous school*.

Findings revealed no significant differences in the performance of the learners in both the pre- and post-tests when grouped according to *sex* (p-values=0.861, 1.000, respectively). This means that the sex of the learners, whether male or female, does not matter with his/her number knowledge readiness. This concurs with the study of Pina et al. (2021) where they concluded that males outperform females in math do not hold true in the key mathematical areas. However, Ogden et al. (2023) found that in mathematics, boys received higher ratings in the academic achievement than girls in fourth grade. In the OECD TIMSS (Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study) 2007 survey, boys outperformed girls in Grade 4, but between 2011 and 2015, girls' scores remained stable, while boys decreased, thereby closing the gap in mathematics (Borgonovi et al., 2018 as cited by Ogden et al., 2023).

Findings also revealed no significant differences in the performance of the learners in both the pre- and post-tests when grouped according to *previous school* (p-values=0.154, 0.115, respectively). This means that the previous school of the learner does not matter

with his/her number knowledge readiness. In contrast, there are large differences in the frequency with which students from seemingly similar schools reach high achievement levels (Ellison and Swanson, 2016).

Conclusions and Recommendations

Based on the findings gathered, it was concluded that the number knowledge readiness of the pupils significantly improved as evidenced by the pre- and post-test results. This further implies that the class discussion and activities of the teachers helped improve their readiness and prepared them for the next level of learning. It was also concluded that the learners' sex and previous school do not have any bearing with their number knowledge readiness.

As such, it is hereby recommended that the teachers continue to employ varying activities that could boost the performance and readiness of the learners. The school may also implement activities for teachers to be continually equipped with the necessary skills in making the learners ready as there were still learners that definitely and probably need help. The future researchers may conduct similar research by looking into other areas of readiness and by considering other profile variables that could contribute to or affect the learners' readiness.

Conflict of Interests

No conflict of interest.

References

- Arpilleda, A.J., Resullar, M.P., Budejas, R.P., Degorio, A.L.G., Gulle, R.T., & Somera, M.C.J. (2023). Learning Gap Assessment in Integrated Mathematics 9. *Brillo Journal*, 3(1), 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.56773/bj.v3i1.39>
- Borgonovi F., Ferrara A., & Maghnouj S. (2018). *The gender gap in educational outcomes in Norway*. OECD Education working paper no. 183.
- Chi, C. (2023, December 9). Philippines still lags behind world in math, reading and science — PISA 2022. *Philstar.com*. Retrieved from <https://www.philstar.com/headlines/2023/12/06/2316732/philippines-still-lags-behind-world-math-reading-and-science-pisa-2022>
- Chiang, I. A., Jhangiani, R. S., & Price, P. C. (2015, October 13). *Quasi-Experimental research*. Pressbooks. Retrieved from <https://opentextbc.ca/researchmethods/chapter/quasi-experimental-research/>
- Ellison, G., & Swanson, A. (2016). Do schools matter for high math achievement? Evidence from the American mathematics competitions. *American Economic Review*, 106(6), 1244-1277. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1257/aer.20140308>
- Kid Sense. (2023, January 5). School readiness - Kid sense Child Development. *Kid Sense Child Development*. Retrieved from <https://childdevelopment.com.au/areas-of-concern/school-readiness/>
- Ogden, T., Olseth, A., Sørli, M.-A., & Hukkelberg, S. (2023). Teacher's Assessment of Gender Differences in School Performance, Social Skills, and Externalizing

Behavior From Fourth Through Seventh Grade. *Journal of Education*, 203(1), 211-221.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/00220574211025071>

Pina, V., Martella, D., Chacón-Moscoso, S., Saracostti, M. & Fenollar-Cortés, J. (2021). Gender-Based Performance in Mathematical Facts and Calculations in Two Elementary School Samples From Chile and Spain: An Exploratory Study. *Front. Psychol.*, 12, 703580. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2021.703580>

School Readiness Test (SRT). (n.d.-b). Retrieved from https://ststesting.com/srt_des.html?fbclid=IwAR2YhFTvmDZY8zYPbISekfZ7_6-VROOrVIa3HG388XFM6i7EFTHwv26lF-g

